

RESEARCH ARTICLE**USAGE OF LEAFY VEGETABLES BY THE NATIVE OF
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Abstract:

A total of 31 plant species belonging to 23 families were recorded, which were used as leafy vegetables by the native of Barpali NAC, Bargarh district, Odisha, India. The data were documented as botanical name followed by local name, family, plant parts used, and their mode of use. The dominated family is Brassicaceae, which contributes five (16.1%) species; both the families Amaranthaceae and Cucurbitaceae contribute three (9.7%) species each. The rest of the 20 families contributed one species each. Out of 31 plant species, 21 (68%) are herbs, three (10%) are shrubs, five (16%) are climbers, and two (6%) are trees. Leafy vegetables like *Amaranthus oleraceus*, *A. viridis* L., *Basella alba* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Cucurbita maxima* Duchesne, *Coriandrum sativum* L., *Glinus oppositifolius* (L.) A.DC., *Ipomoea aquatica* Forssk., *Marsilea minuta* L., *Moringa oleifera* Lam., *Portulaca oleracea* L., and *Spinacia oleracea* L. were most commonly used by the natives of the study site. A significant portion of the tribal population relies more on wild leafy vegetables compared to those that are cultivated and also gets revenue by selling the wild leafy vegetables. The wild leafy vegetables were collected in the vegetative stages from the various parts of the study sites, like home gardens, grazing land, forests, watercourses, etc. Results clearly indicate that there is a need for an awareness program on local resources in the study site.

Keywords: Leafy Vegetables, Barpali NAC, Bargarh.

Introduction:

In India, more than 53 million tribal people depend on natural resources for their daily needs (Bharucha and Preety, 2010). Further, wild vegetables are a key constituent of traditional food systems around the world (Turner *et al.*, 2011). The Indian lifestyle is speedily altering into a developed way of life; the habit of taking in the wild plants and plant parts as food has not been eliminated. In addition,

people grow a few crops and also collect wild edible plants to meet their daily needs. The human diet is dominated by a single staple food and a lesser amount of other food substances, resulting in a high risk of poor consumption of both macro- and micronutrients in many developing countries. In India, rice and wheat are the staple diet; other food substances like vegetables, pulses, fruit, fish, and other animal products contribute less to the diet. Leafy green vegetables are main sources of nutrition like proteins, carbohydrates, oils, beta carotene, folic acid, ascorbic acid, phenols, minerals, etc. (Mishra and Mishra, 2013). To protect against diet-related chronic diseases, the World Health Organization (WHO) endorses a daily intake of >400 gm of fruit and vegetables per person per day (WHO, 2013). The growing of ethnobotanically useful plant species in the surrounding area of the home has been a long practice in several cultural groups of the world. Such a fraction of land is usually known as a kitchen garden or home garden, which provides various benefits (Buchmann 2009). In early times, people growing and maintaining different plant species in the surrounding area of the home and making their products by family members were mainly for the family consumption purpose. On the other hand, the altering socioeconomic circumstances along with the initiation of profitable business have introduced the concept of cash with home gardens. In the home garden, a growing number of species collectively not only deal with making resources available for food and medicine but also expose community mechanisms associated with flexibility strategies by avoiding risk and dropping liability, as may be noticed generally in single-crop cultivation (Buchmann 2009). Home garden practices are even common in the ancient tribal groups of northeast and central India (Srivastava and Heinen 2005). Green leafy vegetables help to fight against belly bloat, make you kingly and low, relieve anxiety, improve inflammatory response, support healthy aging, control the toxins, boost digestive enzymes, and also maintain immunity. Mostly these leafy vegetables are short-lived. As leafy vegetables perform photosynthesis, their vitamin K level is high. The most common form of this vitamin, i.e., phylloquinone, is directly involved in photosynthesis. We can add these leafy vegetables to our diet in many ways, including salads, soups, juices, sauces, curries, etc. Keeping these in mind, the present study deals with the use of leafy vegetables by the native peoples of Barpali NAC of Bargarh district, Odisha, India.

Materials and Methods:

Study Area and Data Collection

Barpali is one of the four N.A.C.s in Bargarh district. The area is located at 21.1922° N latitude and 83.5879° E longitude. Barpali N.A.C. consists of 11 wards, its area is 31.7793 square kilometers, and its population is about 20841 (Sahu *et al.*, 2024). In order to document the utilization of native leafy vegetable plants, the study area was visited regularly, and close communication was made mostly with the tribal people. Plant specimens were collected and identified with local flora (Saxena and Bramhan, 1994-96). Personal interaction was made with 24 vendors, including 18 (75%) men and six (25%) women, having an age group of 30–50 years. The information about the uses of the selected plants was documented, and photographs were taken. The botanical names, local names, and families were checked by using local flora books (Saxena and Brahman, 1994-1996). The local names of the collected species were cross-checked by using previously published reports by various authors in Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2010; Sahu *et al.*, 2013; Sahu *et al.*, 2016; Sahu *et al.*, 2020; Sahu *et al.*, 2021; Sahu and Ekka, 2021; Sahu and Sahu, 2017, 2019; Sahu and Mishra, 2022; Mishra and Sahu, 2022; Behera and Sahu, 2023; Sahu and

Raal, 2024). The botanical name, local name, families, and mode of uses of collected species were described in detail.

Plant Enumerations:

1. *Allium cepa* L., Local Name: Uel, Family: Amaryllidaceae, Mode of uses: young leaves and shoots are collected, roasted then eaten.
2. *Amaranthus spinosus* L., Local Name: Kanta Leutia, Family: Amaranthaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked with mustard oil, chilly, salt with potato and then consumed.
3. *Amaranthus tricolor* L., Local Name: Lal khada, Family: Amaranthaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young shoots are cut into small pieces, cooked with salt and chilly and then eaten.
4. *Amaranthus viridis* L., Local Name: Leutia saga, Family: Amaranthaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young shoots along with other vegetables are cooked and used as curry.,
5. *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss., Local Name: Lim, Family: Meliaceae, Mode of uses: Fresh tender leaf along with flower is fried with mustard oil.
6. *Bacopa monnieri* (L.) Pennell., Local Name: Brahmi, Family: Scrophulariaceae, Mode of uses: Young shoots are cooked and then eaten by tribal people.
7. *Basella alba* L., Local Name: Poi, Family: Basillaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked with mustard oil, chilly, garlic, salt and then eaten.
8. *Bauhinia purpura* L., Local Name: Kuelar, Family: Caesalpiniaceae, Mode of uses: Young leaves are collected, mixed with brinjal, onion, oil, salt and cooked as curry and taken.
9. *Boerhavia diffusa* L., Local Name: Gadhapurni, Family: Nyctaginaceae, Mode of uses: Tender leaves are cooked with mustard oil, chilly, salt and then eaten.
10. *Brassica napus* L. var. *glauca* (Roxb.) Schulz, Local Name: Surso, Family: Brassicaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are roasted with mustard oil and then adding brinjal is cooked and then consumed.
11. *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L., Local Name: Phula-kobi, Family: Brassicaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are fried or made into curry and consumed.
12. *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L., Local Name: Bandha Kobi, Family: Brassicaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are fried or made into curry and consumed. Leaves also used to prepare Manchurian.
13. *Brassica oleracea* L. var. *gongylodes* L., Local Name: Goint kobi, Family: Brassicaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are fried or made into curry and consumed.
14. *Cinnamomum tamala* Nees., Local Name: Tejpatra, Family: Lauraceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are used as spice in making curry.
15. *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott, Local Name: Saru, Family: Araceae, Mode of uses: Young tender leaves and leafy shoots are collected, cut into small piece, cooked with salt and chilly then eaten.
16. *Corchorus capsularis* L., Local Name: Nalita, Family: Tiliaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked with mustard oil, chilly, salt with potato and consumed as food.
17. *Coriandrum sativum* L., Local Name: Dhania, Family: Apiaceae, Mode of uses: Tender leaves are collected, curry is prepared and eaten.
18. *Cucurbita maxima* Duchesne., Local Name: Makhan, Family: Cucurbitaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young stems are collected, roasted then eaten.
19. *Glinus oppositifolius* (L.) A.DC., Local Name: Pitasaga, Family: Molluginaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked in mustard oil using oil, chilly, salt and garlic along with brinjal.

20. *Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam., Local Name: Kanda, Family: Convolvulaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young stems are cooked with mustard or ground nut oil and garlic then consumed with rice.
21. *Lagenaria siceraria* (Molina) Standley, Local Name: Laoo, Family: Cucurbitaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young stems are cooked with other vegetables.
22. *Marsilea minuta* L., Local Name: Sunsunia, Family: Marsileaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked with mustard oil, and garlic paste.
23. *Mentha spicata* (L.) emend. Nathh., Local Name: Podina, Family: Lamiaceae, Mode of uses: Young leaves paste adding salt chilly is used as chantey.
24. *Momordica charantia* L., Local Name: Karla, Family: Cucurbitaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are eaten after frying or roasting.
25. *Moringa oleifera* Lam., Local Name: Munga, Family: Moraginaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked dried and also with mung dal and vegetables used as curry.
26. *Murraya koenigii* L. Spreng., Local Name: Lesinga, Family: Rutaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are used as spice in curry and give it a specific scent. Roasted leaf pieces are used in various food materials for batter taste.
27. *Polygonum plebeium* R.Br., Local Name: Muthisaga, Family: Polygonaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young shoot are roasted with mustard oil and then adding brinjal is cooked and then consumed.
28. *Portulaca oleracea* L., Local Name: Chanti sag, Family: Portulacaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves and young stems are collected, roasted then eaten.
29. *Raphanus sativus* L., Local Name: Mula, Family: Brassicaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are fried along with other vegetables.
30. *Spinacia oleracea* L., Local Name: Palanga, Family: Chenopodiaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are fried with vegetables and also cooked with dal and potato to make dalma curry.
31. *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L., Local Name: Methi, Family: Fabaceae, Mode of uses: Leaves are cooked with mustard oil, and garlic dried and adding vegetables also taken as food.

Results and Discussion:

A total of 31 plant species belonging to 23 families were recorded, which were used as leafy vegetables by the natives of Barpali NAC, Bargarh district, Odisha, India (Figure 1). The data were documented as botanical name followed by local name, family, plant parts used, and their mode of use. The dominated family is Brassicaceae, which contributes five (16.1%) species; both the families Amaranthaceae and Cucurbitaceae contribute three (9.7%) species each. The rest of the 20 families, i.e., Amaryllidaceae, Apiaceae, Araceae, Brasillaceae, Caesalpiniaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Convolvulaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, Lauraceae, Marsileaceae, Meliaceae, Moraginaceae, Nyctaginaceae, Polygonaceae, Portulacaceae, Rutaceae, Scrophulariaceae, and Tiliaceae, contributed one species each (Table 1, Figure 2). Out of 31 plant species, 21 (68%) are herbs, three (10%) are shrubs, five (16%) are climbers, and two (6%) are trees (Table 2, Figure 3). Leafy vegetables like *Amaranthus oleraceus*, *A. viridis* L., *Basella alba* L., *Chenopodium album* L., *Cucurbita maxima* Duchesne, *Coriandrum sativum* L., *Glinus oppositifolius* (L.) A.DC., *Ipomoea aquatica* Forssk., *Marsilea minuta* L., *Moringa oleifera* Lam., *Portulaca oleracea* L. and *Spinacia oleracea* L. were most commonly used. A significant portion of the tribal population relies more on wild leafy vegetables compared to those that are cultivated and also gets revenue by selling the wild leafy vegetables. The wild leafy vegetables were collected in the

vegetative stages from the various parts of the study sites, like home gardens, grazing land, forests, watercourses, etc.

Table 1: Family wise distribution of leafy vegetable species used by the native of Barpali NAC, Bargarh district, Western Odisha, India

Name of Family	No. of species	% age of Contribution
Amaranthaceae	3	9.7
Amaryllidaceae	1	3.2
Apiaceae	1	3.2
Araceae	1	3.2
Basillaceae	1	3.2
Brassicaceae	5	16.1
Caesalpiniaceae	1	3.2
Chenopodiaceae	1	3.2
Convolvulaceae	1	3.2
Cucurbitaceae	3	9.7
Fabaceae	1	3.2
Lamiaceae	1	3.2
Lauraceae	1	3.2
Marsileaceae	1	3.2
Meliaceae	1	3.2
Molluginaceae	1	3.2
Moraginaceae	1	3.2
Nyctaginaceae	1	3.2
Polygonaceae	1	3.2
Portulacaceae	1	3.2
Rutaceae	1	3.2
Scrophulariaceae	1	3.2
Tiliaceae	1	3.2

Table 2: Habit wise plant distribution of study sides

Habit	No. of species	% age of contribution
Herb	21	68
Shrub	3	10
Tree	2	6
Climber	5	16

Figure 1: Photographs of representative leafy vegetables namely *Allium cepa* (a), *Amaranthus spinosus* (b), *Amaranthus tricolor* (c), *Amaranthus viridis* (d), *Azadirachta indica* (e), *Bacopa monnieri* (f), *Basella alba* (g), *Bauhinia purpurea* (h), *Boerhavia diffusa* (i), *Brassica napus* (j), *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* (k), *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* (l), *Brassica oleracea* var. *gongylodes* (m), *Cinnamomum tamala* (n), *Colocasia esculenta* (o), *Corchorus capsularis* (p), *Coriandrum sativum* (q), *Cucurbita maxima* (s), *Glinus oppositifolius* (t)

Figure 2: Family wise distribution of leafy vegetables used by the native of Barpali NAC of Bargarh district, Western Odisha, India

Figure 3: Pie-chart showing diversity of plant species by habit of the study sites

Out of the 31 leafy vegetables in the present study, 12 species, viz., *Allium cepa* L., *Amaranthus viridis* L., *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss., *Basella alba* L., *Bauhinia purpurea* L., *Boerhavia diffusa* L., *Brassica napus* L. var. *glauca* (Roxb.) Schulz, *Corchorus capsularis* L., *Coriandrum sativum* L., *Mentha spicata* (L.) emend. Nathh., *Moringa oleifera* Lam., and *Raphanus sativus* L., were reported for their ethnomedical uses by the natives of Bargarh district of Odisha. (Sahu *et al.*, 2010). Out of the 31 leafy vegetables in the present study, 11 plant species (*A. cepa* L., *A. tricolor* L., *A. viridis* L., *A. indica* A. Juss., *B. alba* L., *B. napus* L. var. *glauca* (Roxb.) Schulz, *B. variegata* L., *B. diffusa* L., *C. sativum* L., *M. spicata* (L.) emend. Nathh., and *M. oleifera* Lam.) were reported for ethnomedicinal uses by the people of the Sohela block, Bargarh district of Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2013). Leafy vegetables like *A. cepa* L., *A. indica* A. Juss., *Brassica* sp., *Cinnamomum tamala* Nees., *Mentha* sp., and *Murraya* sp. were used for oral and dental health care by the natives of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu and Sahu 2017). Similar kinds of results were also reported by various authors that were described as below. Mohanty and Routray (2018) reported the leafy vegetables used in and around the Gandhamardan hills and Nrusinghnath of Bargarh district. They recorded 43 green leafy vegetables, among which about 25 species were similar to my survey report. In their report they did not mention any specific medicinal use of a specific plant that was mentioned in this document. Parida and Mahalik (2020) studied seven tribal communities to assess the diversity of plant species and documented 48 species belonging to 26 families; among those, Amaranthaceae was the dominant species, containing eight plants. Various parts of plants, like *A. cepa* L., *A. indica* A. Juss., and *M. oleifera* Lam., were used for oral care by the natives of Kalahandi district, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2020). Rana *et al.*, (2020) reported regarding the use of leaves of *C. tamala* Nees. To cure indigestion and headache by the Gond tribal community of Amlipali villages of Padampur N.A.C., Bargarh district, Odisha. Sahu *et al.*, (2021) reported the ethnomedicinal uses of *A. indica* A. Juss. and *B. diffusa* L., plants for the treatment of various diseases by the Sahara Tribal Groups of Kangaon Village of Bargarh District in Western Odisha. Sahu and Ekka (2021) reported the use of a total of 39 plant species from 26 families as leafy vegetables by the natives of Bargarh district, Western Odisha, India. Sahu and Sahu (2022) reported a total of 44 plant species belonging to 27 families were recorded as leafy vegetables by the tribal peoples of the Jharigaon block of Nabarangpur district, Odisha. Dash and Sahu (2023) reported about the use of 49 leafy vegetables from 28 families by the natives of the Balangir district, Odisha. Rout and Sahu (2023) reported *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. For the treatment of skin diseases, diabetes, and antiseptics by the natives of the Bhawanipatna area, Kalahandi district. Sharma *et al.*, (2024) looked into the phytochemical components of *Marsilea minuta* leaves, which are in charge of a number of documented pharmacological characteristics. The phytochemical screening identified a number of bioactive substances, including tannin, saponin, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and reducing sugars, that were present in three distinct extracts (aqueous, methanol, and ethanol). These secondary metabolites demonstrate antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities. Padhan *et al.*, (2025) reported regarding the ethnomedicinal use of various parts of *Moringa oleifera* Lam by the native of Bargarh district, they also reported the phytochemical screening of the same plant.

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